

Influence of Street Hawking on Secondary School Students' Psychological Wellbeing in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State.

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Abstract

The study investigated influence of street hawking influence on the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. It was a survey study that adopted descriptive method. Five hundred and forty two (542) students participated in the study. Street Hawking and Psychological Wellbeing Questionnaire (SHPWQ) was used to obtain the data for the study. The psychometric properties of the instrument were established. The content validity of the instrument was done by three experts in the field of Educational Evaluation and Counselling Psychology. The reliability of the two instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha method and the coefficient values of .797 and .878 were obtained for psychological well-being and socio-economic status scales respectively. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, t test and linear regression. The findings revealed that street hawking negatively influenced students' psychological disposition. It equally revealed those parents' socio-economic status influences students' involvement in street hawking and a difference exist in psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by location. Sequel to the findings, it was recommended among others that advocacy campaign, seminars and symposia should be organised by school counsellors to educate parents and guardians on the negative effects of street hawking on students' psychological wellbeing.

Key words: Street hawking, students, psychological wellbeing.

Introduction

In an attempt to survive and meet the necessities of life, people engage in different economic activities like trading which include street hawking. Street hawking is a type of trade that involves the selling of goods/items along the road and from one place to another. It is the movement of a trader from one location to another in search of customers for patronage in the purchase of the goods/items he seeks to sell. It is a practice of selling items by young and old people who move from street to street, putting the seller closer to the buyer. This type of trade is common in the major cities (urban areas) in Nigeria. It appears that various streets and roadsides in the cities, towns and suburbs in Nigeria are getting increasingly congested with the activities of street hawkers. Among these hawkers are secondary school students who struggle to make a living

by peddling various items along the streets and roadside daily when in fact they should be in school. This situation is worrisome as many secondary school students appear to be more involved in street hawking today in Nigeria than ever.

The Nigeria economic situation seems to have contributed to the involvement of secondary school students' involvement in street hawking. Parents with low income/poor living condition who are financially poor are forced to saddle their secondary school children the tasks of peddling items to augment their meagre income. Failed parenting sequel to spouse divorce or death of parent(s) could be a possible reason for secondary school students' involvement in street hawking. It involves both male and female students of different age bracket. According to Olutunde (2013) everywhere you go in cities, towns and some villages, children whose ages are mostly between seven years and above, hawk on streets and this is no longer considered an odd sight in Nigeria. Early adolescents (10-13 years) may more likely be engaged in street hawking compared to their counterparts in late adolescence (aged 17-19). Such persons are often characterized by being on and off school because they are engulfed in the everyday battle for survival and financial gain which plunge them into street hawking, minor trading, car washing, bus conducting and cattle rearing in the metropolitan areas (Dada, 2013).

Involving secondary school students in street hawking is considered a form of child abuse because it endangers the health (physical, psychological, and social) and safety of the children, interferes with their education, and deprives them the right to normal and happy childhood. Hence, Aderinto (2006) posited that secondary school students' involvement in street hawking is at the expense of their education which poses a threat to society's long term survival. Beside, street hawking has arrays of risks on the wellbeing of the students. It is crucial to highlight that the impact of street hawking on the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who hawk is enormous. They are susceptible to abuses of different kinds, leaving them with emotional trauma and equally denying them the opportunity to socialize with each other in school and home environments. The major concern is their susceptibility to being raped which is one of the major problems in the society today that can be partly associated with street hawking. If sexual harassment could occur in offices, then its prevalence on the streets remains inevitable. Besides, they often contribute to motor accidents on the road, endangering other road users and themselves. According to Shailong et al (2011) and Ekpenyong and Sibiri (2011) motorists injured 84% street hawkers and about 40% respectively as respondents concurred to accident being a major threat to street hawkers. Some of the hawkers who got injured from accidents became paralysed while some even died from the injuries (Akpan & Oluwabamide, 2010).

The sudden increase of street hawking in Nigeria may be attributed to various factors. It can be attributed to rapid population growth in Nigeria which is closely associated with high rate of unemployment, inflation, low wages and deplorable working conditions of civil servants hence secondary school students attempt to help and support their families. Another possible cause of street hawking could be poverty. Poverty could be the most significant rifest factor for street hawking. In the opinion of Oguntola (2019), hawking is "a culture of economic poverty," given that a large proportion of Nigerians live in abject poverty. In the view of Adinde (2020), street hawking is a phenomenon common in developing countries. In Africa and Nigeria in particular, informal economic activities serve the need to provide solutions to societal problems of poverty, unemployment, and make consumer goods accessible to the populace. Kazeem (2018) boldly asserted that Nigeria has become the poverty capital of the world, which has increased street

hawking. In the opinion of Agbo (2017) poverty is a dominant factor in child-street hawking, which is a form of child labour. Some secondary school students voluntarily take part in child labour for survival. According to Ojie (2015) poverty has forced many Nigerian school age adolescents to abandon school to help their families earn some extra income by hawking wares on the streets at most hours of the day and night. The search for money to make ends meet in a depressed economy is obviously one of the major reasons for parents and guardians sending their children or wards to hawk. Oli (2018) submitted that poverty and inequality are major causes of secondary school students' involvement in hawking on the streets. By implication, poor families are consequently handicapped in having relatively few employable persons of the prescribed working age. There is thus a heavy pressure of dependency mostly on young adolescents of poor families and this situation leads them to hawking on the streets to enhance their living standard. Most of the students that hawk are either in the primary or secondary school. At the end of each day's sales, they become weak and tired that they are unable to concentrate, contribute to discussion or study on their own (Chrisantus, 2020).

Street hawking has tremendous negative impact on the young adolescents, especially their psychological wellbeing. The elements of psychological well-being according to Feller et al. (2018) include a sense of emotional balance, thoughts and social relationships. Some studies Baland and Robinson (2000) and Anagbogu (2000) revealed that secondary school students who are involved in street hawking suffer low self-esteem, inferiority complex emotional distress, exhaustion, and personality disorders. They are denied the right to family interaction as they spend more time on the street and can barely even cope at school with academic work. The resultant impact could be feeling of dejection and frustrated both at home and in school. Hence, Ekpenyong and Sibiri (2011) noted that street trading is one of the great menaces affecting both the individual and society. The study of Emeri and Adelanwa (2019) on the Impact of street hawking on social adjustment of secondary school students revealed a significant negative impact of street hawking on their social adjustment.

When in-school adolescents are involved in street hawking certain behaviours and practices are inevitable. They are involved in different kinds of behaviour including; careless and nonchalant attitude, immoral relationships with opposite sex and peer groups influences or joining unions to secure their relationship and also to negotiate on their behalf with the law enforcers. These have grave consequences on them and their family. Actual and potential hazards associated with street hawking have in many instances manifested in ways that should have drawn both government and non-governmental interventions. Mitullah (1991 cited in Uthman, (2019) noted that female street vendors are often harassed to obtain licenses of operation and sometimes the female hawkers are sexually abused by enforcement agencies which often lead to health hazard, especially in the area of sexually transmitted diseases. This situation could lead to the spread of HIV/AIDS and other incurable diseases.

Street hawking effect can be exacerbated by different variables like family socio-economic status. This refers to the relative position of the family in a social system in which individuals are ranked according to their access to or control of wealth, power and status. Parents with little or no formal education earn little income due to lack of marketable skills, which cannot meet the family needs. In this situation, parents force their school age children to hawk in order to augment household incomes (Ojie, 2015). Some families cannot afford to pay school fees of their wards or maintain their education they have no option than to withdraw them from school. Many of these

children are into domestic service and street trading to assist their families in making ends meet (Uthman 2019). Some families depend on hawking for a living. Statistics showed that as high as 64% of in-school adolescents or school age children work as street hawkers in Nigeria (Femi, 2011). About 45% of them have dropped out of school and worked full-time as street hawkers to enhance the family economy. On the average, the children contribute 1 USD daily working as street hawkers (Femi, 2011). Ago (2014) carried out a study on the impact of street hawking on the girl child academic performance in government day junior secondary schools in Yobe state. The result of Logistic regression showed that adolescent girl's involvement in street hawking could be predicted by their socio-economic status (parent's occupation) and family size (father's number of wives and number of children). Similarly, Ugochukwu (2012) study on socio-demographic characteristics of street vendors in Nnewi, Anambra state, had a sample of 147 teenagers; 90 boys and 57 girls aged 8-19years. The findings revealed that poverty, low socioeconomic status and the inability to raise family income are the major reasons they are found on the streets during school hours trying to fend for themselves and their family.

Street hawking in the metropolis in Nigeria is part of everyday life. School age adolescents, (male and female) are involved in the practice, often chasing moving vehicles at traffic points on highways. Some are full-time street hawkers selling all sorts of fruits and food under the sun and sometimes in the rain. In 2006, two Nigerian non-governmental organizations, Youth and Environmental Development Association (YEDA) and Community Action for Participation in Social Sector (COMPASS) teamed up to retrieve about 102 young girls in Kano State from street hawking back to school, an indication that there appear to be more female hawkers than male. This is consistent with Ashimolowo et al (2010) that most (60.8%) school age adolescents who engaged in street hawking are females while (39.2%) are males. This shows that there are more female school age adolescents involved in street hawking activities than their male counterparts. In an attempt to justify the above claim, Paul et al (2019) study in Wukari revealed more female involvement in street hawking with 84%, while male teenage hawkers were 16%. In the same, Magaji and Sarka (2020) revealed that female (82.9%) are more in street hawking with a mean age of 13 years than their male counterpart. Majority were from large family who were mostly polygamous. Their major reasons for hawking were to assist their parents in buying household items and to augment their parents' income. Similarly, Obioha and Ngwa (2021) examined gender and social issues in teenage hawking. The findings revealed that bullying, sexual harassment from both male and female, rape and kidnapping were common to both genders and social abuses experienced by teenage hawkers with a significant gender disparity amongst the victims with female teenagers more exposed than males (73% to 27%).

Another variable of interest is age of the secondary school students. Studies identified their age bracket to fall between 10 and 19 years (Ashimolowo et al. 2010). Street hawking has left many in-school adolescents out of school as they drop out, withdrawn by their parents or not enrolled. School age adolescents estimated to be 10.5 million are out of school in Nigeria (Jerome-mario 2022). They are engaged in income generating activities to contribute to the sustenance of the family (Ubah & Balus, 2014). According to the International Labor Organization (2012), the number of working children under the age of 14 in Nigeria is estimated at 15 million. The high level of diverse and tedious jobs that children execute in dangerous circumstances is alarming. Ijadunola et al. (2015) study revealed that early adolescents (10-13 years) were more likely to engage in street hawking compared to their counterparts in late adolescence (aged 17-19).

Location is an important variable of interest in this study. In-school adolescents (secondary school students) in the urban as well as rural areas are involved in the street hawking activities. Dada (2013) asserted that the use of school age as hawkers, beggar and bus conductors are widespread in urban areas. In every major city in Nigeria school age children appear to be involved in street hawking more in the urban than in the rural areas. In Western (Ibadan, Ondo and Ogun) and Eastern parts (Onitsha, Enugu and Owerri) of Nigeria, it is observed that children may attend school in the morning or afternoon and hawk goods outside of school hours, though some children trade on the streets the whole day. While in the Northern part of Nigeria they are engaged in street begging. The income they obtain helps their parents or house madams financially or pays for their school fees. Hoyano and Keenan (2007) opined that people who migrate from rural areas to urban areas in search of better prospects are often ill-prepared for urban life and therefore forced to either use their school age young adolescents or others to enhance their economic situation.

Statement of the Problem

The dramatic increase of secondary school students' involvement in street hawking in Nigeria has reached a worrisome state. It is precipitated on various factors like the rapid population growth in Nigeria, high rates of unemployment, low wages and deplorable working conditions of most low wage earners. It is essentially economic related issue which is significantly associated with poverty level of the people. Poverty is predicated as the most anticipated reason for street hawking in Nigeria. The search for money to make ends meet in a depressed economy is obviously one of the major reasons for parents and guardians sending their school age wards to hawk. Oli (2018) submitted that poverty and inequality are major causes of young adolescents hawking on the streets. In the light of this, Agbo (2017) and Oguntola (2019) have opined that hawking is "a culture of economic poverty," and poverty is a dominant factor in child-street hawking, which is a form of child labour. According to Ojie (2015) poverty has forced many Nigerian school age adolescents to abandon school to help their families earn some extra income by hawking wares on the streets. Most of them who hawk are either in the primary or secondary school, or at the end of each day's sales, they become weak and tired that they are unable to concentrate, contribute to discussion or study on their own (Chrisantus, 2020).

Although street hawking appears to contribute to the family's economy the hazards associated with it appear to outweigh the predicted economic rewards. The popular streets of Benin metropolis like every other major city in Nigeria are not left out of these social vices. Often times, those in-school adolescents who are involved in street hawking are exposure to sexual molestation, bullying, theft, and other forms of antisocial behaviours. Such experience is capable of leaving the children with an indelible psychological trauma. Thus, most secondary school students involved in street hawking appear to have a maladjusted behavioural disposition to life. Consequently, they exhibit some antisocial behaviour like aggression, low self-esteem, complacency towards criminal tendencies etc. These are indicators of ill balanced emotional and psychological individual. It is in view of the above that this study aims at investigating influence of street hawking on the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State.

Research Question

To guide the study, the following research question was raised

1. Does the involvement of secondary school students in street hawking influence their psychological wellbeing?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Parents' socio-economic status will not significantly influence secondary school students' involvement in street hawking in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State.
2. There will be no significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by location (urban and rural areas).
3. There will be no significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by sex.
4. There will be no significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by age.

Methodology

The study adopted the survey research design principally meant to substantiate the influence of the independent variable (parents' socio-economic status, age and sex) on the dependent variable (psychological well-being) of students in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria. The population of the study consists all public Junior and senior secondary school 1 and 2 students in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State, with a numerical strength of 8,085 (Ministry of Education, Benin City, 2023 statistics). The sample size was 542 students obtained from six secondary schools from the 12 secondary schools in Egor local Government Area. Multistage random sampling technique was used to obtain the sample size. The first stage was to identify the 12 secondary schools in the local government area. The second stage was to classify the schools into urban and rural areas. The third stage was to enlist the schools into coeducational and non- educational schools. Through simple random sample techniques of balloting with replacement three schools were selected from urban and rural areas each, making a total of six sampled schools. Through simple random sampling techniques 100 students (50 each in JSS and SSS) were sampled making a total of 600 students who were involved in street hawking. At the end of the exercise only 542 respondents questionnaire could be used with the attrition of 58 respondents' instrument. The research instrument that was used was a self-structured questionnaire titled "Street Hawking and Psychological Wellbeing Questionnaire (SHPWQ). The instrument has two (2) sections namely; Section A and B. Section A comprised respondents' demographic profile. Section B has items that elicited response from respondents on street hawking and psychological well-being. The questionnaire was a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) with a value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 for all positively worded items and reverse for all negatively worded items. The psychometric properties of the instrument were established. The content validity was ascertained by experts in the field of counselling Psychology, while the reliability co-efficient value of .797 and .878 were obtained for psychological well-being and socio-economic status respectively, through Cronbach Alpha statistical method.

The researchers sought the consent of the school authorities for permission to have access to their students after explaining the intention of the study. With the permission of the school authorities the researchers met with the students and sought their consent after explaining the purpose of the research exercise. The instrument was then administered to the students in their classrooms with the aid of a research assistant and the completed copies were retrieved the same

day. Descriptive statistic of mean and standard deviation were used to answer question one and inferential statistics was used to analyse the hypotheses.

Results

The results of the study are presented in the table below.

1. Research question 1: Does the involvement of secondary school students in street hawking influence their psychological wellbeing?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistic of Mean and Standard Deviation on the Influence of Street Hawking on the Psychological Wellbeing of Secondary School Students.

		Mean	Std.	Remarks
1	Sexual Harassment	2.80	0.67	Agreed
2	Negative Emotions.(Fear)	3.41	0.73	Agreed
3	No time to socialize with friends	2.83	0.82	Agreed
4	Being unhappy	3.31	0.62	Agreed
5	Exposure to road traffic danger	3.20	0.65	Agreed
6	Loneliness and Isolation	3.38	0.75	Agreed
7	Aggressiveness	3.55	0.69	Agreed
8	Exposure to harsh weather conditions	3.53	0.73	Agreed
	Scale Average	3.25	0.71	Negative

N= 542, Cut-Off Mean = 2.50

Table 1 shows the descriptive data of the influence of street hawking on the psychological wellbeing of students. From the table, all items have mean values greater than 2.50 for a four points likert scale. This implies that the respondents agreed to all the stated items. Also the composite average is equally greater than 2.50. This implies that the respondents agreed to the negative influence of street hawking on their psychological wellbeing with aggressiveness (3.55), exposure to harsh weather conditions (3.53) and negative emotion –fear (3.48) respectively as the items with the highest mean.

Hypothesis 1: Parents' socio-economic status will not significantly influence secondary school students' involvement in street hawking in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State.

Table 2: Linear regression of parents' socio-economic status on secondary school students' involvement in street hawking in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State.

Model	Sum of Square	df	mean square	F	Sig
Regression	702.599	1	702.599	54.973	.000
Residual	6901.646	540	12.781		
Total	7604.245	541			

Table 2a shows the F value of 54.973, P value of .000 tested at an alpha level of .05. The P value is less than the alpha value. This implies that parents' socio-economic status significantly influence school children involvement in street hawking in Edo State. Therefore the hypothesis that says parents' socio-economic status will not significantly influence secondary school students involvement in street hawking in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State is rejected and the alternate is accepted. In conclusion, parents' socio-economic status significantly influences secondary school students' involvement in street hawking in Edo State.

Table 2b: Model Summary of the contribution of parents’ socio-economic status on secondary school students’ involvement in street hawking in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State.

Model	R	R ²	R ² Adjusted	Std Error of the Estimate
Parents’SES	.304	.092	.091	3.57503

Table 2b shows the relative contribution of parents’ socio-economic status to school children involvement in street hawking in Benin City. The Table shows R² value .092 (9.2%) contribution of parents’ socio-economic to secondary school students’ involvement in street hawking in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by location (urban and rural areas).

Table 3: Independent Sample t-test of Difference in Psychological Wellbeing of secondary school students’ involved in street hawking by location (urban and rural areas).

Location	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	df	t-value	p-value (Sig. 2-tailed)
Urban	327	31.70	4.15	540	2.158	.031
Rural	215	31.00	3.00			

$\alpha = .05,$ $p < .05$ **Significant**

Table 3 shows difference in psychological wellbeing of school children involved in street hawking in urban and rural areas of Edo State. From the table, the number of Urban respondents N=327 while Rural N = 215. Their Mean values are 31.70 and 31.00 while standard deviations are 4.15 and 3.00 respectively. The t-value of 2.158 is significant, because, the p-value (.031) is less than alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that street hawking influences the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students differently with respect to their location (urban/rural). From the mean values of 31.70 > 31.00 for urban and rural students, it shows that street hawking has psychological impact on the urban dwelling students than those in the rural area.

Hypothesis 3: There will be no significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by sex.

Table 4: Independent Sample t-test of Difference on the Psychological Wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by Sex

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	p-value (Sig. 2-tailed)
Male	129	30.76	2.83	540	2.309	.021
Female	413	31.63	3.97			

$\alpha = .05,$ $p < .05$ **Significant**

Table 4 shows difference in psychological wellbeing of male and female students' street hawkers. From the table, the number of respondents male N=129 while female N = 413. Their Mean values are 30.76 and 31.63 while standard deviations are 2.83 and 3.97 respectively. The t-value of 2.309 is significant, because, the p-value (.021) is less than alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that street hawking influences the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students differently with respect to their sex. From the mean values (31.63 > 31.76) it implies that street hawking has more psychological impact on the female students than their male counterparts.

Hypothesis 4: There will be no significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of secondary school students who are involved in street hawking by age.

Table 5: Independent Sample t-test of Difference on the Psychological Wellbeing of secondary school students Street Hawkers by Age

Age (years)	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	p-value (Sig. 2-tailed)
9 – 13 years	282	32.09	3.23	540	4.356	.000
14 – 19 years	260	30.71	4.13			

$\alpha = .05,$ $p < .05$ Significant

Table 7 shows difference in psychological wellbeing of students' street hawkers within their age brackets. From the table, the number of respondents between 9 – 13 years N=282 while 14 – 19 years N = 260. Their Mean values are 32.09 and 30.71 while standard deviations are 3.23 and 4.13 respectively. The t-value of 4.356 is significant, because, the p-value (.000) is less than alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that street hawking influences the psychological wellbeing of the students in the various age brackets differently. From the mean values (32.09 > 30.71) it implies that street hawking has more psychological impact on the younger (9 – 13 years) students than the older (14 – 19 years) ones.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that street hawking negatively influenced students' psychological well-being as it impacts on their emotions capable of leading to aggression, antisocial behaviour and delinquency. This finding could be attributed to factors like harsh and unfriendly environment where the street hawking is done hence; those involved in it are psychologically perturbed. This finding corroborates the assertions of Anagbogu (2000), Emeri and Adelanwa (2019) that street hawking leads to emotional distress, inferiority complex and social adjustment. It could be that the students who engage in street hawking become weak and stressed after daily sales as they are exposed to different harsh weather and environmental hazard. Thus, confirm the assertion of Chrisantus (2020) that children at the end of each day's sales will be too weak and tired to engage in any meaningful academic task

The findings of the study revealed that parents' socio- economic status influenced school children involvement in street hawking. This finding can be attributed to the poverty level of most low income parents with low socio-economic status who in Nigeria evidently have more children (4 to 7) than they can conveniently cater for. Due to the parents' inability to raise fund for the

children's education, the children are forced to engage in street hawking in an attempt to raise fund for themselves and assist their poor parents. This corroborates the assertion of Ojie (2015) and Agbo (2017) who asserted that poverty is the dominant reason why school children are involved in street hawking in Nigeria as the proceeds from it augment the family income. The study further revealed that parents' socio-economic status account for 9.2% of school children involvement in street hawking.

The findings equally revealed a significant difference in the psychological wellbeing of in-school children who are involved in street hawking by location. The study revealed that school children in urban areas are more psychologically affected than their counterparts in the rural areas. This finding can be attributed to the fact that the secondary school students in urban areas who are involved in street hawking may have been invited by their guardians to the city from the villages with the hope and promise of better life in the city. The shock of being forced to hawk in the streets against their expectation on the premise they were taken from their poor parents in the village can heighten their psychological problems. This finding corroborates the assertion of Hoyano and Keenan (2007) that people who migrate from rural areas to urban areas in search of better prospects are often ill-prepared for urban life and therefore forced to either use their school age children or other school age children to enhance their economic situation.

The findings equally revealed a significant difference in school children involvement in street hawking by sex. It showed more female children involvement in street hawking than their male counterpart. This can be attributed to different reasons. It could be an expression of a kind of denial and apathy towards the girl child's access to education. Although generally, children involvement in street hawking is a kind of child abuse, this finding presupposes the premium most parents in Nigeria place on their girl child even in the 21st century. This finding is in consonant with the assertions of Ashimolowo et al (2010), Paul et al (2019) and Magaji and Sarka (2020) that more female children are involved in street hawking activities than their male counterparts. It implies that the girl child has the higher possibility of being psychologically disoriented as she is exposed to the different negative indices inherent in street hawking.

Besides, street hawking's psychological impact was found to significantly differ by age. The study revealed that younger school age children were more psychologically affected than the older ones. This can be attributed to the harsh weather and environment where street hawking takes place which is apparently beyond the coping capacity of these younger children. Ijadunola et al. (2015) study revealed that early adolescents (10-13 years) were more likely to engage in street hawking compared to their counterparts in late adolescence (aged 17-19). This finding corroborates the assertion of Ijadunola et al. (2015) that young adolescents (10-13 years) were more likely to engage in street hawking and under dangerous circumstances.

Conclusion

Sequel to the findings of this study, it was concluded that street hawking has negative impact on the psychological/emotional wellbeing of secondary school students who engaged in it in Edo State. It was equally concluded that Female students within the age bracket of 9-13 years were more involved in street hawking than male and older school age children in Edo State.

Implications/Recommendations

The findings of the study are revealing and interesting. They show the destructive nature of street hawking to the psycho-emotional stability of secondary school students, the would be

leaders of the next generation of Nigerians. This implies that street hawking is in fact another form of child abuse as it does not enhance the value of life of the secondary school students who indulge in it. It directly increases and breeds young people who take to antisocial and criminal activities in the society. This is predicated on the fact that an emotionally and psychologically unstable child can easily be cajoled into unhealthy, antisocial and criminal activities.

In the face of these therefore, there should be advocacy campaign and sensitization programme by school counsellors to educate parents and guardians on the psychological effects of street hawking on school age children. In schools where Parents Teacher Association exist, the school management should employ that medium to reach out to all parents on the need to stop sending their school age children either before or after school hours to hawk in the street. Symposia and seminars should be organized to draw the attention of everyone to the negative effects of street hawking on the psychological wellbeing of school children.

Besides, the Local Government Authority, State and Federal should ensure the implementation of compulsory education for all school age children. They should ensure the promulgation of law and corresponding sanctions for parents or guardians whose school age children or wards are found engaged in street hawking when the child ought to be in school. More so, rehabilitation centres should be established in all the local Government Areas where children found in street hawking should be taken to for rehabilitation. This would likely reduce the number of young people who are recruited by some criminals into the criminal squad in our society via street hawking.

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